

Industrial Manipulator Parametric Identification

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Abstract—High precision industrial applications call for equally precise functioning of industrial manipulators, which in turn requires accurate modeling of the manipulators. This paper carries out a detailed study on the modeling of industrial manipulators with elastic joints to improve their accuracy. In particular, the effect of adopting a simple harmonic drive (HD) model and ignoring a dynamic effect called low inertia coupling between the actuators and links on the model accuracy has been analyzed from a parameter estimation perspective. Since the aforementioned model characteristics have been generally ignored for high gear reduction ratios, this study is carried out with five different reduction ratios ranging from low to high, where three different models of a three-joints elastic manipulator are considered. The accuracy of the models is compared using the torque performance metrics of a predefined joint motion of the robot. Furthermore, the impact of the models with different accuracy is assessed by carrying out a state-of-the-art dynamic parameter estimation, and the resulting errors are compared to ascertain the merits of adopting a detailed elastic dynamic model of a manipulator.

Keywords—Flexible joints, Modelling errors, Manipulators.

I. INTRODUCTION (HEADING 1)

In modern days, industrial manipulators play a vital role to achieve quality products at low cost and time. The growing demand for quality particularly increases the need for accuracy in manipulator applications. In robotic measurement applications, the accuracy requirements for manipulators are even greater, in the order of $[\mu\text{m}]$. These requirements can only be met with accurate dynamic models that can facilitate precise pose estimation and control of manipulators. Lately, to reduce the overall cost of operation and for safety concerns, lightweight and elastic manipulators are mostly sought after. The inclusion of elasticity makes it even more challenging to model the non-linear dynamics of a manipulator with high accuracy and to control it effectively. Several types of models have been used to represent the dynamics of industrial manipulators and estimate their corresponding parameters to simulate their dynamic motion. The most common one is a rigid body model, which assumes the joints and links to be rigid. This model has been used extensively in many parameters estimation works [1]–[6] to estimate the various inertial parameters—mass, center of mass, and inertia of each link. Interestingly, in [7], by ignoring some dynamic terms and estimating link-side torques, an elastic joint model is adapted to make use of the rigid joint model structure to estimate inertial parameters. On the other hand, citing the insufficiency of the rigid body models to accurately capture highly non-linear dynamics of manipulator systems, several different types of works have been proposed to enhance the model accuracy: in [8], the parameters are estimated offline using the rigid body models and further tuned online using a neural network to capture the dynamics which is not represented by the models. Although such online tuning approach has been fairly successful, it requires a large amount of data that encompasses different movements of the robot, which is difficult to achieve in practice; and as an alternative, online adaptive controllers have been proposed to compensate for the model inaccuracy, as reported in [9].

Interestingly and importantly, a closer look at the aforementioned elastic models reveals the following facts:

1) a simplified version of the complete elastic model ignored the low inertia coupling terms between the link and actuator dynamics; and

2) no separate model has been considered for the transmission system elements.

Both the facts are based on the assumption that the additional torque contributed by them is relatively small due to high joint reduction ratios, and doing so simplifies the model. Accordingly, this study aims at understanding the effects of ignoring low inertia coupling terms and transmission system models on the robot’s model accuracy, and thereby, propose an elastic manipulator model which can potentially improve the model’s accuracy. In particular, the work makes the following contributions: 1) a detailed elastic model error analysis of ignoring low inertia coupling terms and adopting a simple HD model; 2) the aforementioned error analysis repeated across a range of transmission ratios to understand its effect and to quantify the resulting error; and 3) impact of less accurate elastic models of a manipulator on the estimation of its dynamic parameters/coefficients.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

First, The dynamic equations of motion for an elastic joint robot in its general form can be written as given in [14] as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{q}) & \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{q}) \\ \mathbf{S}^T(\mathbf{q}) & \mathbf{B} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \ddot{\mathbf{q}} \\ \ddot{\theta} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}) + \mathbf{c}_1(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}, \dot{\theta}) \\ \mathbf{c}_2(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}) \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{q} - \theta) \\ \mathbf{K}(\theta - \mathbf{q}) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \boldsymbol{\tau} \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{D}(\dot{\mathbf{q}} - \dot{\theta}) \\ \mathbf{D}(\dot{\theta} - \dot{\mathbf{q}}) \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{c} , \mathbf{g} , \mathbf{K} , and \mathbf{D} are the link and actuator inertia matrix, Coriolis and centrifugal terms, gravity terms, joint stiffness, and damping matrices respectively. In (1), \mathbf{q} and θ are the link and motor side joint angles respectively, and $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the motor side torque. The link and motor side equations in (1) are coupled through the elastic torque $\boldsymbol{\tau}_j = \mathbf{K}(\theta - \mathbf{q})$ at the joints and also via $\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{q})$ the low inertia coupling matrix. In (1), two factors have often been overlooked in the conventional elastic models that can potentially affect the accuracy of those models and these are discussed below:

1) *Low Inertia Coupling*: \mathbf{S} is usually a constant in the planar case or zero in the case of robots which has 2 links with orthogonal joint axes. In other general cases, \mathbf{S} is usually ignored due to large reduction ratios (100-150), which reduces the coupling effect of \mathbf{S} [14]. This simplifies the elastic model significantly but it also reduces the model’s accuracy to some extent. The exact effect of ignoring \mathbf{S} on the elastic model’s accuracy has never been studied extensively in complex robotic systems, and this has been done in this work.

2) *Simplified Harmonic Drive Model*: Another important term that is being traded off for simplicity is the \mathbf{B} matrix which includes the models of various transmission elements used for each robot joint. Since harmonic drives are more common in the robotics field, they are considered here. HD includes three main

components: a wave generator, flex spline, and cylindrical spline. Of the three components, flex spline is flexible, and the joint elasticity is mainly due to this component.

For this study, we have considered three different numerical models: 1) mod_1 with a simple HD model, 2) mod_2 with a relatively complex HD model, and 3) mod_3 . with a complex HD model and S . A virtual model (mod_{ad}) developed using MSC.Adams software is used for comparison.

III. SYSTEM SETTINGS FOR ANALYSIS

A manipulator with three non-coplanar elastic joints has been considered in this work to analyse the effect of low inertia coupling and HD model. The system has 3 movable links with a reach of 1:5 m and weighs 139 kg. A 3- dimensional (3D) model of the system is shown in Fig. 1a.

Fig. 1a A virtual model of a 3 joint elastic robot modelled in Adams.

Fig. 1b A virtual model of a 3 joint elastic robot modelled in Adams.

The virtual model includes the HD model but not the belt-pulley for each joint, and in the HD, the flex spline is modeled as a rigid body. These are done to keep the virtual model relatively simple and easy to use. The implementation of joint elasticity for a single joint in Adams is shown in Fig. 1b. In particular, the figure shows joint 3 connecting Link 2 and Link 3. In Fig. 1b, cylindrical spline is fixed to Link 2 and revolute joints are defined for rotor (R_{rotor}), wave generator (R_{WGen}), and flex spline (R_{FSpl}) keeping Link 2 as the reference. The motion transmission obtained due to the belt-pulley system is replicated by defining a coupler joint of ratio rb between R_{rotor} and R_{WGen} .

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In order to deduce the estimation error for each model i , the true Ψ^i vector is computed for each one using the actual values of the dynamic parameters, and the relative estimation error vector Ψ_{err}^i in percentage is computed as shown below:

$$\Psi_{err}^i = \left(\frac{\Psi_{ls}^i - \Psi^i}{\Psi^i} \right) \times 100$$

Again, the individual elements of Ψ_{err}^i of different models cannot be compared directly due to the number of parameters and its various linear combinations. Hence, the overall estimation accuracy of mod_1 , mod_2 , and mod_3 are compared by segregating the error into three categories: low (0-20%), mid (21-50%), and high (51-100%). Figure 2 compares the percentage of Ψ_{ls}^i elements computed for each model mod_i

falling under three different error categories. From the figure, we can see that the relatively simple model mod_1 estimates 62.5% of Ψ_{ls}^i with high error, and only 29.69% of them are estimated with low error.

Fig. 2 The Ψ_{err}^i is categorized into three categories (0-20%, 21-50%, and 51-100%) and the percentage of Ψ_{ls}^i elements falling under each category is compared across three models: mod_1 , mod_2 , and mod_3 .

Fig. 2 compares the percentage of Ψ_{ls}^i elements computed for each model mod_i falling under three different error categories. From the figure, we can see that the relatively simple model mod_1 estimates 62.5% of Ψ_{ls}^i with high error, and only 29.69% of them are estimated with low error. This trend is associated with the fact that mod_1 uses a relatively simple HD model and also ignores the S term. In the case of mod_2 , and mod_3 , though both the models can estimate the same number of parameters, mod_2 doesn't consider the S term. As a result, mod_3 reports a higher percentage (68.42%) of Ψ_{ls}^i estimated with low error when compared to mod_2 which reports a slightly lower value (60.53%). However, with mod_2 , and mod_3 , a significantly higher percentage of Ψ_{ls}^i can be estimated with a lower error when compared to mod_1 . Also, a significantly lower percentage of Ψ_{ls}^i have been estimated with high error using mod_2 (26.32%) and mod_3 (21%) when compared to that of mod_1 . In the mid-range error category, the difference between different models seems to be minimal, with mod_2 reporting a slightly higher value of 13.16%. Overall, mod_2 , and mod_3 estimate more number of Ψ_{ls}^i with lower error, and of which mod_3 being the relatively accurate model performs better across different error categories.

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